

Notes

Alkaline Earth Metal Complexes : Mixed Ligand Complexes of Magnesium Oxinate with some Mono- and Bidentate Ligands

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Manuscript received 29 June 1990, revised 6 August 1992, accepted 12 August 1992

In comparison to transition and rare earth metals, few mixed ligand complexes of magnesium have been reported. Mixed ligand complexes of transition metal salts of 8-hydroxy quinoline are known¹. Mixed complexes of alkali metal salts of 8-hydroxyquinoline with oxygen and nitrogen donor ligands have also been reported².

We report here the synthesis and characterisation of some mixed ligand complexes of magnesium oxinate with different mono- and bidentate ligands.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes (Table 1) are stable under dry condition and absorb moisture slowly when exposed to air. But in case of the complexes formed by pyridine and ammonia, hydrolysis takes place and water molecules replace pyridine and ammonia. These adducts have higher melting points than the stoichiometric mixture of their ingredients; decomposition temperature of the complexes are much higher than that of the ligands, showing their greater stability.

In the ammonia complexes, NH₃ rocking vibration appeared as a new peak at 755 cm⁻¹ suggesting coordination of ammonia molecules to the metal. The disappearance of the O—H band of the second ligand (or its shift of 150 cm⁻¹) and reappearance at 2 700–2 400 or 1 900–1 800 cm⁻¹ suggest that there is strong hydrogen bonding. The 3 380 cm⁻¹ band of ethylenediamine remains unaffected after complexation, but the 3 316 cm⁻¹ band appears at 3 250 cm⁻¹ with reduced intensity in the complexes. The NH₂ bend vibration appears as shoulder at 1 605 cm⁻¹.

In the catechol adducts, one of the O—H stretching frequency of catechol is absent and the second O—H stretching frequency is shifted down by about 200 cm⁻¹. Further a new broad band of medium intensity with maxima at 2 700 cm⁻¹ and another at 2 640 cm⁻¹ are observed in the complex. The presence of the coordinated glycol is inferred by comparing the glycol peaks in the complex Co(glycol)₃Br₃, Ca(bzac)₂glycol and glycol itself (Table 2).

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*/ (Colour)	Analysis % Found/(Calcd.)			
	C	H	N	M
Mg(8HQ) ₂ .2Py (Yellow)	71.00 (71.48)	4.40 4.68	11.55 11.90	5.00 5.10
Mg(8HQ) ₂ .en (Pale yellow)	63.65 (64.51)	5.00 5.37	14.82 15.05	6.21 6.45
Mg(8HQ) ₂ .1N2N (Green)	68.49 (69.42)	3.35 3.72	8.42 8.67	4.52 4.95
Mg(8HQ) ₂ .ONP (Yellow)	63.42 (64.00)	3.40 3.55	8.91 9.33	4.90 5.33
Mg(8HQ) ₂ .Sa1H (Yellow)	68.82 (69.28)	3.61 3.92	6.18 6.46	5.17 5.54
Mg(8HQ) ₂ .catechol (Grey)	67.82 (68.24)	3.91 4.26	6.41 6.63	5.32 5.68
Mg(8HQ) ₂ .glycol (Pale yellow)	63.38 (64.17)	4.21 4.81	7.10 7.48	5.93 6.41
Mg(8HQ) ₂ .o-phen (Pale yellow)	67.93 (68.57)	4.52 4.75	12.95 13.33	5.43 5.71
Mg(8HQ) ₂ .AnthA (Grey)	66.49 (66.96)	3.83 4.01	9.03 9.37	4.97 5.35

*8HQ ≡ 8-Hydroxyquinoline, Py ≡ pyridine, en ≡ ethylenediamine, 1N2N ≡ 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, ONP ≡ o-nitrophenol, Sa1H ≡ salicylaldehyde, o-phen = o-phenylenediamine, AnthA ≡ anthranilic acid.

Compared to the anhydrous compound, the hydrated one show an extra ir peak at 860 cm⁻¹ which may be due to the rocking mode of coordinated water³.

TABLE 2—IR SPECTRA (cm⁻¹) OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	O—H str.	C—O str.	(CH ₂) rock
Glycol	3 330	1 086, 1 040	832, 863
Co(Glycol) ₃ .Br ₃	3 280	1 077, 1 065, 1 035	877, 858
Co(bzac) ₂ -glycol	3 300	1 099, 1 036	889, 860
Mg(oxin) ₂ .glycol	3 100 - 3 050	1 080, 1 045	870, 845

Experimental

In the general method of preparation, a slight excess of the second ligand was added to the suspension of dehydrated magnesium oxinate (obtained by heating the hydrated salt above 154°) in absolute ethanol in 1:1 mole ratio. The corresponding complexes separated out, were washed with cold absolute ethanol and dried (90°). In some cases the adducts were also synthesised by placing the dehydrated magnesium oxinate in an atmosphere of the second ligand (ammonia, pyridine and ethylenediamine).

Acknowledgement

Thanks of the authors are due to the C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for providing a Junior Research Fellowship to one of them (S.K.S.).

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